

Assessment of bronchial wall thickness in secondary childhood and adults(12-19 years old) comparison with theoretical models

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Abstract

A thickened bronchial wall is the morphological substratum of most diseases of the airway. Theoretical and clinical models of bronchial morphometry have so far focused on bronchial lumen diameter, and bronchial length and angles, mainly assessed from bronchial casts. However, these models do not provide information on bronchial wall thickness. This paper reports *in vivo* values of cross-sectional wall area, lumen area, wall thickness and lumen diameter in ten healthy subjects as assessed by multi-detector computed tomography. A validated dedicated software package was used to measure these morphometric parameters up to the 14th bronchial generation, with respect to Weibel's model of bronchial morphometry, and up to the 12th according to Boyden's classification. Measured lumen diameters and homothety ratios were compared with theoretical values obtained from previously published studies, and no difference was found when considering dichotomic division of the bronchial tree. Mean wall area, lumen area, wall thickness and lumen diameter were then provided according to bronchial generation order, and mean homothety ratios were computed for wall area, lumen area and wall thickness as well as equations giving the mean value of each parameter for a given bronchial generation with respect to its value in generation 0 (trachea). Multi-detector computed tomography measurements of bronchial morphometric parameters may help to improve our knowledge of bronchial anatomy *in vivo*, our understanding of the pathophysiology of bronchial diseases and the evaluation of pharmacological effects on the bronchial wall.

Keywords: bronchial anatomy; human; image processing; *in vivo*; MDCT; morphometry.

Introduction: Many current knowledge of lung physiology in human is mainly based on pulmonary function and relies on pulmonary functional tests (PFTs). However, many physiological parameters (resistance of the conducting airway tree, dynamics of flow through bronchi and responsiveness to various physiological or therapeutic events) depend on the geometric properties of bronchi (Bates, 1993).

In vivo conducting airway morphometry has seldom been reported so far, due to the difficulty of imaging complex three dimensional (3D) structures. Morphometric studies of the bronchial tree have previously been performed in a small number of cadavers of different species (Weibel & Gomez, 1962; Weibel, 1963; Horsfield & Cumming, 1968; Horsfield et al. 1976; Hooper, 1977; Phillips & Kaye, 1995). Some of these models describe airway length and diameter as a decreasing function of the order of generation, predicting the mean bronchial length and diameter of each generation as a function of trachea length and diameter (Weibel & Gomez, 1962; Weibel, 1997; Mauroy et al. 2004). Nevertheless, due to the method used, no information could be obtained on bronchial wall thickness. In addition, few studies have assessed bronchial morphometric parameters *in vivo*. Sauret et al. (2002) and Tawhai et al. (2004) recently focused on bronchial length, diameter or angulations assessed on human bronchial casts and *in vivo* on ovine and human bronchial trees using multi-detector computed tomography (MDCT) 3D imaging. These parameters are fundamental to simulate flow and inhaled particle transport (van Erftbruggen et al. 2005). Bronchial wall thickness (WT), however, has still not been fully evaluated, and WT changes may be a substantial indicator of

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the efficiency of inhaled treatments and in various pathological processes (Boser et al. 2005; Montaudon et al. 2007a). The evaluation of bronchial WT could benefit from recent MDCT developments that help to obtain isotropic images of bronchi in any reconstructed plane. For this purpose, 3D software packages enabling *in vivo* measurements of cross-sectional wall area (WA) and cross-sectional lumen area (LA) of any visible bronchus on MDCT have been developed (Palagyi et al. 2005; Brillet et al. 2007) and validated (Montaudon et al. 2007b). The aims of our study were (1) to measure bronchial lumen diameter (LD) obtained by 3D quantitative thinsection CT in a population of adult healthy subjects, (2) to compare these measurements with values predicted by various theoretical models and (3) to provide a range of normal values for bronchial WA, LA, WT and LD for a given generation

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects

All subjects gave their written informed consent to participate in the study, which was approved by the ethical committee of the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Bordeaux. MDCT scans of ten subjects (nine males and one female) were prospectively used to carry out this study. Scans were obtained from healthy subjects referred to exclude parenchymal blebs before scuba diving. None of them presented a clinical history of thoracic disease, abnormal MDCT findings (including bronchial dilatation) or abnormal PFT results. Mean subject age was 39.2 (range 21–58) years.

Description of the software

A dedicated software tool (SAB-3D: software for analysing bronchi in three dimensions) had been conceived to skeletonize the bronchial tree and to reconstruct 2D thinsection CT images orthogonal to the main bronchial axis of bronchi visible on MDCT scans in order to perform wall area and lumen area measurements. This software enabled analysis of the bronchial tree according to the bronchial generation and has been previously validated (Montaudon et al. 2007b). Briefly, it was based on two successive post-processing steps (Fig. 1). The first step provided 2D reformatted images strictly perpendicular to the central axis of any bronchus assessable on axial MDCT scans. They were obtained as follows: a first segmentation extracted from the MDCT data the airway tree using a seeded region growing algorithm (de Dietrich & Braquelaire, 2004; Montaudon et al. 2007b). Then, a seedvoxel was placed in the trachea on the first slice of the acquired volume. All voxels which density was included between two thresholded values and contiguous to the seed were iteratively added to the seed-voxel, leading to the construction of a binary volume of the bronchial tree. A geodesic distance transform, propagating on the binary volume surface from the selected seed voxel, allowed us to extract isocontours separated one from another by a constant distance (10 voxels). An automated computation of the local centre of each isocontour was then performed, and local centres were connected in order to obtain the skeleton of the bronchial tree. The computed skeleton could be superimposed on the binary volume, supplying information about bronchial 3D orientation and division order (Fig. 1b). Errors in the computation of the skeleton at the point of large bronchi divisions (mainly the trachea, as shown in Fig. 1b) may occur, but are circumvented by using a greater distance for isocontour definition. Thinsection CT scans orthogonal to the skeleton were reconstructed between two contiguous local centres, giving cross-sectional images of any desired bronchus (Fig. 1c,d). The second post-processing step was an automated segmentation using a Laplacian of Gaussian algorithm to detect airway contours and perform semi-automated measurements of LA and WA, as previously described and validated (Fig. 1e) (Berger et al. 2005; Montaudon et al. 2007b).

Using this software, we were able to assign each segmented bronchus to a generation according to Weibel's (1963) model, i.e. downwards from trachea to distal generations. We also indicated the bronchial generation according to a slightly modified Boyden (1955) classification: a bronchus was named according to its ventilated pulmonary segments. For example, the right superior lobar bronchus was named B1-3 and the left one B1-5. For each measured bronchus, the generation was assessed according to Weibel's model and the modified Boyden classification, and the software provided WA and LA. Assuming the hypothesis that bronchi are round on cross-sectional reformatted slices, LD was calculated using the formula $2\sqrt{(LA/\pi)}$. Mean WT was calculated as the difference between the total bronchus radius and the lumen radius, $(\sqrt{[(WA + LA)/\pi]} - \sqrt{(LA/\pi)})$. Lastly, we calculated for each parameter (WA, LA, WT and LD) the ratio between two contiguous generations. Bronchial LD and ratios were then compared with the theoretical results as assessed in previously published studies (Murray, 1926; Weibel, 1963, 1997; Mauroy et al. 2004).

Fig. 1 SAB-3D software applied to a chest MDCT acquisition. Volumetric data of a thorax examination were used to reconstruct 1-mm thin-section CT images (a), from which a propagation algorithm allows us to obtain a binary volume and subsequently a skeleton of the airway tree (b, frontal view). An error occurred in the skeletonization of the tracheal division, but this was not detrimental to measurements of main bronchi morphometric parameters. Seven contiguous cross-sectional reconstructions of a bronchus perpendicular to its central axis are shown (c). The selected bronchus belonged to the fifth generation and the anterior segment of the right upper lobe; this is shown on the native CT section (a, arrowhead), and the binary volume and skeleton (b, arrow). The thin section on which measurements were performed was chosen with the minimum of contiguity with surrounding vessels (d, open arrowhead shows the selected bronchus). Detection of airway contours by a Laplacian of Gaussian algorithm was then performed (e, empty arrowhead)

to provide automated measurements of LA and WA.

RESULTS

Using Boyden's modified classification, the division of the Table 2 provides comparisons per generation between bronchial tree was found as follows: trachea gave two measured LD and HR and theoretical LD and HR values daughter branches, B1-10 (main bronchus) in ten subjects. averaged over subjects. Using Weibel's generation classification,

In the right lung, B1-10 bifurcated in B1-3 and B4-10 in cation, a significant difference was found between measured ten subjects. B1-3 trifurcated in B1, B2 and B3 in eight and expected LD when using Mauroy's equation but not subjects, bifurcated in B1-2 and B3 in one subject, and when using Weibel's one. By contrast, using Boyden's bifurcated in B1a + 3 and B1b + 2 in one subject, so this classification downwards from segmental bronchi, no patient did not have a segmental bronchus for the apical difference was found. No difference was also found when segment of the right upper lobe. B4-10 bifurcated in B4-5 comparing measured HR and theoretical HR whatever the and B6-10 in eight subjects, and trifurcated in B4-5, B6 and ordering of generations used, except for the 0.79 value of B7-10 in two subjects. B4-5 always bifurcated in B4 and B5. HR and Boyden's classification.

B6-10 bifurcated in B6 and B7-10 in all subjects ($n = 8$). B6 Plots show that LD was underestimated up to generabifurcated in nine cases and trifurcated in one case. In ten tion 8 of Weibel's classification, and up to generation 6 of subjects, B7-10 gave B7 and B8-10 and the latter bifurcated Boyden's classification (Fig. 2). LD of downwards generations

Table 1 Comparison of lumen diameters and homothety ratios assessed by MDCT in each subject against the theoretical results based on Weibel's and Boyden's models

Subject	No. of bronchi	Generation no. (W)	LD _m vs. LD _t (W)	LD _m vs. LD _t (M)	HR _m vs. HR _t (0.79)	HR _m vs. HR _t (0.85)
1	156	10	0.016	< 0.001	NS	NS
2	246	12	0.029	< 0.001	NS	NS
3	288	12	0.02	< 0.001	NS	NS
4	339	13	NS (Wr)	< 0.001 (Wr)	NS	NS

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5	257	12	0.04	< 0.001	NS	NS
6	185	13	NS	< 0.001	NS	NS
7	289	10	< 0.001	< 0.001	NS	NS
8	271	14	NS	< 0.001	NS	NS
9	199	10	0.02	< 0.001	NS	NS
10	338	13	NS (Wr)	0.001 (Wr)	NS	NS
Subject	No. of bronchi	Generation no. (B)	LD _m vs. LD _t (W)	LD _m vs. LD _t (M)	HR _m vs. HR _t (0.79)	HR _m vs. HR _t (0.85)
1	156	7	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
2	246	8	NS (Wr)	0.043 (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
3	288	10	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
4	339	9	NS (Wr)	0.028 (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
5	257	10	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
6	185	9	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
7	289	9	NS (Wr)	0.028 (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)
8	271	12	NS	NS	0.038	NS
9	199	8	NS (Wr)	0.043 (Wr)	NS	NS
10	338	9	NS (Wr)	NS (Wr)	NS	NS

For each subject, values are *P*-values from comparisons between mean measured values and theoretical values per generation.

No. of bronchi: number of assessable bronchi; Generation no. (W): number of generations assessed using Weibel's model; Generation no. (B): number of generations assessed using Boyden's classification; LD_m: measured lumen diameter; LD_t: theoretical lumen diameter; HR_m: measured homothety ratio; HR_t: theoretical homothety ratio according to Weibel's study (0.79) and to Mauroy's study (0.85). Comparisons were achieved using paired *t*-test or Wilcoxon rank-sum test (Wr).

Fig. 2 Plots of mean lumen diameter over all subjects on a logarithmic scale (log LD) against bronchial generations according to Weibel's model (left graph) and Boyden's classification (right graph). Black circles: log of measured LD; open circles: log of theoretical LD calculated with the

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mean measured HR; dashed line: log of theoretical LD calculated using an HR value of 0.79 (Weibel); dotted line: log of theoretical LD calculated using an HR value of 0.85 (Mauroy).

Table 2 Comparison of mean lumen diameters and mean homothety ratios assessed by MDCT versus those calculated using Weibels and Boyden’s models

Generation (W)	No. of bronchi	LD _m (mm)	LD _t (W) (mm)	LD _t (M) (mm)	HR _m	HR _t (0.79)	HR _t (0.85)
0	10	18.55	18.55	18.55			
1	20	13.89	14.72	15.77	0.75	0.79	0.85
2	40	10.42	11.68	13.40	0.75	0.79	0.85
3	92	6.82	9.27	11.39	0.65	0.79	0.85
4	190	4.96	7.36	9.68	0.73	0.79	0.85
5	366	3.56	5.84	8.23	0.72	0.79	0.85
6	538	2.81	4.64	7.00	0.79	0.79	0.85
7	500	2.52	3.68	5.95	0.90	0.79	0.85
8	357	2.45	2.92	5.05	0.97	0.79	0.85
9	219	2.36	2.32	4.30	0.97	0.79	0.85
10	107	2.37	1.84	3.65	1.00	0.79	0.85
11	66	2.30	1.46	3.10	0.97	0.79	0.85
12	49	2.07	1.16	2.64	0.90	0.79	0.85
13	12	1.95	0.92	2.24	0.94	0.79	0.85
14	2	1.84	0.73	1.91	0.94	0.79	0.85
P		NS (Wt) < 0.001			NS NS		

Generation (B)	No. of bronchi	LD _m (mm)	LD _t (W) (mm)	LD _t (M) (mm)	HR _m	HR _t (0.79)	HR _t (0.85)
0	10	18.55					
1	20	13.89					
2	149	8.22					
3	197	5.06	5.06	5.06			
4	392	3.60	4.02	4.30	0.71	0.79	0.85
5	634	2.69	3.19	3.66	0.75	0.79	0.85
6	631	2.28	2.53	3.11	0.85	0.79	0.85
7	365	2.16	2.01	2.64	0.95	0.79	0.85
8	116	2.06	1.59	2.25	0.95	0.79	0.85
9	38	1.96	1.27	1.91	0.95	0.79	0.85
10	12	1.90	1.00	1.62	0.97	0.79	0.85
11	2	1.78	0.80	1.38	0.94	0.79	0.85
12	2	1.84	0.63	1.17	1.03	0.79	0.85
P		NS NS			0.02 NS		

For each generation, values are number of assessable bronchi (No. of bronchi), mean lumen diameter measured on MDCT scans per subject and averaged over subjects (LD_m), mean theoretical lumen diameter calculated from trachea diameter using Weibel’s equation [LD_t (W)] and Mauroy’s homothety ratio [LD_t (M)], homothety ratio measured on MDCT scans (HR_m) and theoretical homothety ratio calculated using Weibel’s study [HR_t (0.79)] or Mauroy’s study [HR_t (0.85)].

DISCUSSION

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In this study we used a post-processing software package, previously validated for accuracy *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Montaudon et al. 2007b), for measuring bronchial morphometric parameters on 1-mm MDCT scans. We have compared our measurements with those calculated from theoretical models of bronchial anatomy and provided bronchial WA, LA, WT and LD values according to bronchial generation in healthy adults. When comparing mean HR per generation versus theoretical values for each subject, no statistical difference was found (Table 1). However, when comparing mean measured LD with expected LD, differences were found in all cases when using a 0.85 value for HR and in six of ten with a 0.79 value for HR (Table 1). These differences are likely to be the consequence of a non-strictly dichotomic division of bronchi up to segmental bronchi. This hypothesis is strengthened by the fact that the number of subjects with differences diminishes when considering a more dichotomic classification of bronchial divisions (Boyden's classification). We have also presented here normal values of the different parameters studied (Table 3). Regardless of the parameter considered, when its average values are semilogarithmically plotted against generation, it appeared to lie approximately on a straight line, as shown Fig. 4 for WT. Thus, based on the model of Weibel's equation for calculating mean bronchial LD of any generation and considering that all bronchial parameters are fractal, we proposed different equations that can be used to determine expected WA, LA, WT and LD of any assessable generation of bronchi explored at MDCT (Table 4). These equations expressed the considered parameter as a function of the related parameter of either trachea or of the previous generation.

When comparing measured values of HR averaged over generations and subjects against theoretical values, no difference was found using Weibel's classification of generations. By contrast, differences were found between measured and expected LD values using Mauroy's equation applied to Weibel's classification, but no difference when using Boyden's classification (Table 2). We believe this difference may be related to the equation used to predict theoretical values

Amongst the bronchial parameters that we were able to measure, LD values only have previously been reported on a large number of bronchi per subject (Weibel, 1963, 1997; Horsfield et al. 1976; Horsfield, 1990; Mauroy et al. 2004). Although Weibel's model of airways is the best known, it is not the only one. Notably, Horsfield & Cumming (1968) developed another model of interest when considering airways as asymmetrical dichotomic structures. However, the latter model uses an upward numbering of bronchial generation, from distal generation to trachea. Because the most distal generations are not assessable using MDCT due to the limited spatial resolution of the technique and because the software we used works downwards from trachea, we have chosen for this study to apply Weibel's model and its derived HR. To take into account the impact of asymmetrical dichotomy and bronchial trifurcations occurring in segmental bronchi and upwards, we also used Boyden's classification of bronchi hypothesis is strengthened by the fact that the number of subjects with differences diminishes when considering a more dichotomic classification of bronchial divisions (Boyden's classification). When comparing measured values of HR averaged over generations and subjects against theoretical values, no difference was found using Weibel's classification of generations. By contrast, differences were found between measured and expected LD values using Mauroy's equation applied to Weibel's classification, but no difference when using Boyden's classification (Table 2). We believe this difference may be related to the equation used to predict theoretical values: the trachea LD directly influences LD of all other generations so its measurement must be made with great care. Trachea LD diminishes regularly from its origin to its bifurcation.

CONCLUSION

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We have compared bronchial morphometry in healthy adults performed using a validated software package and 1-mm MDCT section images against those obtained from theoretical models. Despite being valid when studying a population, Weibel's equation applied to individuals may induce an error when determining LD of bronchi from the tracheal diameter. This error is probably due to anatomical variations in bronchial division upward from the segmental level. Finally, we proposed a range of normal values in adults and new equations for predicting WA, LA, WT and LD based on measurements of previous generations assessable on MDCT

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